

Contextual Spacetime and the Making of Classical Reality - Part 2: Tiers of Subjectivity and How Informational Worlds Construct Subjective Amalgamations of Time

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What is Objective Information?

Imagine everything that objectively exists. Now imagine the smallest most infinitesimal things that could make up such an everything. Obviously these things would have to be fundamental and indivisible, since if they are the smallest things that would mean they could not be “made up” of anything else. Furthermore, because they are the “most fundamental and indivisible” things they cannot be different from one another. This is because if they are defined by them being the most “small and indivisible things” that would mean that there can never be one that is larger or “more divisible” than another one. Additionally, differences between things generally has to do with those things having different “properties”. However, if everything is reduced down its most smallest most indivisible constituents, then such things can have no “properties” since they must only be defined by their “fundamentality”. Since they are indivisible there would be nothing “inside” them that can make one of them have different properties than another one. For this reason, they all must be “property-less” and essentially all the same; defined only by the fact that they “objectively exist”.

This is how to make sense of objective information. In fact “information” is not even the right word. After all, information implies the presence of properties which besides for having the base property of “existence” these “iotas” have none that are defined. In this way objective information isn’t actually “information” but rather sheer potential with the ability to combine with each other and “make up” information with properties. Potential information could therefore be eventually translated as “literally anything” but requires having a subjective existence to actually be translated as having those states. After all, purely objectively, there would be no reason to look at the objective iotas of information in any combination of themselves. Objectively they would always exist on their own and never in any combined “configuration”. Only subjectively can these objective bits of information “combine” into entities with different sizes and configurations.

Additionally, because information essentially only has “potential” states when viewed objectively, this means that any objective information could essentially be anything before it is looked at subjectively. This can be likened to a single 0 dimensional point. The 0 dimensional point from afar looks like a single “dot”. However, such a point could in fact have a 1 dimensional real “length” or even a 2 dimensional real “width”. However, looked at only zero dimensionally, its “length” and “width” cannot be surmised since they can be essentially anything from a 0 dimensional perspective. In this way viewing a point as 0 dimensional doesn’t inform how long, wide or high it is. This doesn’t mean that it can’t have a real length, width or height, but rather that when looked at 0 dimensionally, these properties could be literally anything. Objective information could be looked at in this way. In fact, its not even 0 dimensional in the way a point would be. Instead it simply appears as “pure nothingness” with no points or lines at all. However, since there’s not even a point let alone a line, there’s no way to determine where it begins, ends or even what properties it has. Instead, it can be said to simply be “in all states at

once that are potentially expanding” forever. Just like the 0 dimensional point could have “any length, height and width”, the objective information can have any subjective instantiation. However, since the objective information has an infinite amount of potential properties number of configurations can be said to be infinitely expanding.

What is Subjective Information? And how does “Potential Information” Fit in With it?

It is only a subjective existence that essentially provides this “infinitely expanding” objective information with a “dimension” for it to be eventually viewed as taking on real properties. Much like how the 0 dimensional point reveals its length when “placed” inside a 1 dimensional space, the objective information reveals its properties and states when placed inside a subjective state. Having a subjective state in this way is what makes the objective information finite since it provides it with dimensions to exist finitely within. Without this subjective state, the objective information would have no dimensions to exist within and therefore would simply have an infinitely expansive state where it could be in a set of all states at once that is at the same time infinitely expanding.

Now it seems like this conception of objective information paints it as only having the “potential” to exist within all states once it interacts with an observer who essentially makes it exist within a subjective context. However, before it interacts with an observer isn’t it better defined as having no states than infinitely expanding ones (or all states at once)? After all doesn’t something with potential properties essentially not possess those properties until they’re definitive?

Separations of Temporality - Do Different Periods of Time Objectively Exist?

The answer is that outside of an observer or subjective existence there is no “before”, “now” or “after”. Time is a purely subjective phenomenon that is there to perceive of purely objective information. It may seem like there is a past, present and future, but time itself is a subjective concoction and not one that objectively exists. After all, have you yourself even been in the past or future? You may “remember” memories of the past and therefore think that at one point you were “there”. However when remembering the past you essentially did so in the “present”. Moreover, when thinking and anticipating the future you are “still” doing so in the present. Here is where the deceptively intuitive truth rears its head. You’ve never been in the past or future, only in the present. You may ask how things can ever “happen” or “change” if there is only the present? Well the answer is that surely you have experienced change or happenings yet only ever existed in “the present”. It is therefore not counterintuitive to think that “change” can happen in the absence of any allotment of time passing, since this is perfectly in line with the experiences of every observer! They are always in the same “moment of the present” and yet things still seem to change, the only question then is how!

The answer is that it is true that “objectively” there is no delta in time and only the present. Any “dimension” or axis of time is simply a subjective illusion used to conceive of “changing information” in a finite context. After all, what does it mean for something to be objective? It means that it is true regardless of perspective. Therefore objectively, the only moment that ever happens is “the present”. Observers always feel in the present objectively and never at any other point of time. Time is therefore only a way of viewing this subjectively.

Now what does subjectivity even mean? Looking at something subjectively is simply a “certain” way to look at what is objective. This is to say that “something” can only exist in one way objectively but seem to exist in multiple ways subjectively. This can be compared to time. Objectively there is no time and only what is called “the present”. Subjectively however, the information within this “present” could be looked at in a multitude of ways some of which can be translated as the past and future.

Can Entities Possess Simultaneous States?

The reason this concept is counterintuitive is because there is a fundamental assumption that what is “objective” needs to only be in one state of itself because it needs to be the absolute truth of what is taking place. Subjectively sure there can be multiple ways of looking at something but objectively there would need to only be one truth. For example, suppose that there are two ways to look at the color of a particular crayon - as blue or green. Some people see this crayon as blue while others see it as green. Perhaps this difference is due to how certain photoreceptor cells in the retinas of people eyes function. Now subjectively, it can be true that the crayon is “blue” or “green”. However, objectively there is only one truth - that the color of the crayon itself is simply a wavelength of light reflected from the object that the brains of people can process and translate differently. Now this seems to be a perfect representation of the difference between what is objective and subjective right? After all what is objective only has one truth while what is subjective could have multiple truths.

However, I would argue that even the reasoning behind why a crayon appears as blue or green is a deeply subjective one. After all, what are these things called photoreceptors actually? What is objectively what is called light in the first place? It is all just objective information translated already in a subjective way. If one wants to look at these things truly objectively they shouldn't stop at the level of photoreceptors and photons but go all the way back. After all what is purely objective would have to be the “fundamental total truth” of the nature of all things. Sure in the “context” of color, looking at the phenomenon of how photoreceptors respond to wavelength of light may be more objective than just the experience of “green” or “blue”, however confining information to even a “context” of color is already subjectifying it. Objectively there is only the “whole machine” of everything that exists that never changes. Any “subdivision” of this “whole machine” whether it be the conceptions of particles, galaxies or even colors are simply “subjective manifestations” of the information inside the objective machine.

Why Cant Objective Information Be Still?

Now why cant the objective machine be looked at simply as “one thing” that always exists? The answer is because it cannot be “one thing”. Calling it “one thing” essentially provides it with borders which it could not have. After all if it was simply one neatly packed “everything” then how could it be everything at all? What would be “outside” of this one total thing? The fact that it is possible to “conceive” of things outside of an “everything” shows that the everything cannot be “limited” to a single box of “objective everything”. It therefore cant be everything at all. In fact, not only can't “everything” fit in a box but it actually has to be defined by its not having a box at all. Because the concept of “everything” is infinitely inclusive that would mean that there could be no “borders” or box to ever confine it in any way. After all, imagine a single

box of the entire universe. What would ever exist outside of the borders of that box? Sure one could say “nothing” but even that “nothing” would have to be something and be “nothing” in name only. The truth is that the objective states of things cannot be “limited” or confined at all since it must be defined by its infinite expansion in every possible way. This is why objective information can be said to be not “still” but actually infinitely changing. If objective information does not have any properties in the first place and also has no “borders” to confine it, then it must be in a state of “potentially everything at once”. This means that not only could it be “viewed” in any possible configuration of itself but since it has no borders it must also actually be gaining an infinite number of configurations in 0 time. This means that objective information would have to be defined by “infinite expansion”. If one wants to define what is objective as what “truly” exists, then what “truly” exists as everything would be something that is changing infinitely fast at once and therefore can't be only a “still” something.

Infinite Velocity

The last example that I can give in regards to why what exists objectively needs to be constantly changing relates to the notion of infinite velocity. If an entity is moving infinitely fast that would mean there can be no delta between its origin and destination. In this way, it can be said to be at its destination point at the same moment it departs its origin point. Now if this is true then from the perspective of an observer it would be impossible to surmise “where” this entity actually “departed” from and where it “actually” “arrived”. For since it is at both the origin point and the destination point at the same time, with no time having passed then the observer would simply see it as being situated at both of the points at once. It would therefore be “multiple places at once” as it would be existing at both the origin and destination points with 0 delta of time between them.

This notion can be extended to also an entity that not only makes 1 trip in 0 time but multiple trips in 0 time. If an entity can travel from point A to point B in 0 time, then it could also travel from point B to point C in 0 time and then also from C to point D in 0 time. Such can be seen by the formula for velocity: $\text{velocity} = \text{change in distance} / \text{change in time}$. If an entity is going infinitely fast that means there can be no change in time. In this way infinite velocity = $\text{change in distance} / 0 \text{ change in time}$. If there is 0 change in time, that would not only mean that something traveling at infinite velocity could arrive at any destination at the same time it departed its source but also that it could essentially make any number of trips within that timespan as well! (Since the timespan consists of 0 time passed). After all, if the distance from point A to point B is set to X and the distance from point B to point C is set as Y then just as $X/0 = \text{infinity}$ and $Y/0$ would tend to infinity, $X+Y / 0$ should also tend to infinity. This is because the only way infinite velocity is possible is if there is movement in 0 passage of time. Now if there is 0 passage of time and still movement, that would mean that there is essentially no “limiting factor” for movement. Without a limiting factor, not only could an entity travel infinitely fast and be at 2 points at the same time but also at multiple or even “all” points at the same time.

Now considering that for objective entities there could be no change in time (since time is a subjective phenomenon), objective entities would need to be changing “infinitely fast” and have all possible “properties and configurations” that themselves are infinitely expanding at the same

time. When it is therefore said that objective entities have the “potential” to be looked at subjectively in a number of ways, this does not mean that they are in potential states now but could later be in definitive states subjectively. After all there is no time objectively at all so there can be no before or after. Since objectively there is only the “present”, being in a “potential” state of something simply means that the thing is actually in a “state of something”. This would suggest that entities that have a potential property actually do “still have real properties or states”. However, this “state” that such an entity would have is not just “one definitive state”. Rather, it is defined by “multiple states”.

What is Potential?

This is what “potential” actually means. “Potential” is not something that can later become something else. Rather, potential is something that is already objectively there that is not one thing, but rather multiple things. Sure classically, it is thought that “things can only be in one state of themselves at one time”. However, since the universe is experienced by observers classically then of course there is an inherent bias to thinking that “things can only be in one state of themselves at one time”. In reality, perhaps “things can be in multiple states” of themselves of at one time objectively. However, classically where everything is viewed from the viewpoints of observers, things must exist infinitely subjectively which means they must only be in one state of themselves at a time. In this way, when it is said that something has the “potential” to be another way in the future, that does not mean that there is a now where the “thing” isn’t that future thing and a different place called the “future” where that thing could be that future thing. Instead, “that thing” is merely both what it has the potential to be and what it was and is at the same moment objectively speaking. Only subjectively, can this “timeless thing with multiple states at the same time” be conceived as only having one state. However, since subjectively things cannot be “conceived” as having more than one state at a time, a subjective idea of “time” needs to exist in order for objective things with an infinite number of states to be viewed as in only one definitive state of themselves sequentially.

How Objective Things Are Viewed Subjectively

Using this notion that “entities” could be in multiple states with 0 time passing objectively, now actually explains why subjectively there is time and why there “seems” to be subjectively a past, present and future. Objectively, anything is “everything” infinitely expanding at the same time. However, subjectivity itself is defined as the “viewing” of such “objective information” in a certain manner. This act of “subjectifying” objective information is not something that “requires” time but something that always exists. Remember that time just “seems to flow” even though in reality everything just happens in 0 time. When objective information is “looked at” in a certain way or “subjectively” it can no longer be in “all infinitely expanding states at once” since it is now “confined” to only a certain viewpoint of itself. If the objective infinite of everything can be likened to a box-less whole then a subjective instance of it fashions a box inside of that whole. This box essentially “limits” the objective information so that it needs to be “limited” and exist in only certain possible states and not all possible states simultaneously. A subjective “viewpoint” of the “objective” therefore is what makes information finite. Since subjectively, things are finite and limited that means that they cannot “change states infinitely” but are rather now limited by existing in a specific subjective “context”. Therefore, these “objective entities”

when viewed subjectively now cannot infinitely change so are therefore “limited” in how much they could change. This “limiting factor” of change is what is referred to as “time”. It is what essentially “limits” the changing of an entity’s states when inside a subjective context of the objective.

Now how does the past, present and future seem to emerge from this? Also, why does time in the past “feel like it has already happened” and time in the future “feel like it hasn’t happened”? After all, since there is objectively only the present shouldn’t the present always feel like “what is happening” and everything else (both the past and future) feel like they are both not happening? Why is there a distinction between the past and future if they are both objectively not happening and what causes this distinction?

Differences Between the Past, Present and Future

The difference between the past and future is simply “probability” based. The past “feels like it already happened” because it feels as if it “how it happens” is already 100% decided. After all, no one ever says “what do you think will happen in the past?”. This is because it is assumed that what took place in the past is already 100% decided because it happened. The future however is not 100% certain but is dependent on degrees of freedom and many variables. Therefore, one could say “I think in the future things will be a certain way”, but since that “way” isn’t 100% definitive, the future is fundamentally different from the past which is defined by the certain states of things. Sure, elements of the future could be possibly predicted and therefore don’t have a 0% chance of happening; However, their “probability of outcome” is still not 100% even if there are factors that can be used to help “predict” the future. My proposal is that the only thing that separates the past and future is the element of certainty and probability. The past only “happened” because the states of its information are “100% certain” while the future only “will happen” because the probabilities of its informational states are not “100% certain” and only “X% Probable”. In this way, it is not the fact that “events happened already” that make those events as 100% having happened that way, but rather the 100% chance of events happening that way that defines what we call “the past”.

Now if information that exists in the past and future have different probabilities of having certain states, how does this probability come about and how are the probabilities of the states of different informational “things” decided?

Objective Probability

Well first of all, as stated earlier, probability itself is objectively interchangeable with the notion of “entities” having multiple states simultaneously or constantly “changing” states. Therefore, while it is generally thought that assigning probabilities to an entities states is a tool used to predict the entities true one “state”, perhaps it is the opposite. This is to say that what if an entities true one state is simply an understandable way to describe the true ever-changing nature of entities. What this would suggest is that when a coin is flipped and it lands on heads, this would not mean that it truly “landed on heads”. Rather it only seemed to “land on hands” from the perspective of the observer. Objectively, the coin would simply be in “multiple states” at

once, however from the perspective of the observer, the state of the coin is subjectively “viewed” as being in only one definitive state.

This does not mean that when a coin is flipped it is in both states of heads and tails until the moment it falls and turns up as heads or tails. Rather, there is a spectrum of subjectivity that is involved in “flipping” a coin. Firstly, objectively the coin is essentially just “ever-changing objective information” that is everything at once. However, since it is already defined here as a “coin” that means it could not truly be objective. Therefore it is fair to say that if a coin is being flipped, the coin already exists within a somewhat limited “subjective context”. This means that there is already an element of finite time that exists since whenever the state of information is limited, time must be the limiting factor. In this way, the coin can be said to be constantly changing states but not at infinite speed. This means that the coin would change states but at a finite speed so it can't actually be “2 places at the same” like it would if it was objective information. The coin would still be “ever-changing” but now its ever-changing-ness would be bound to a finite limiting factor meaning that its objective infinite change must now be conceived of as “limited” by time. This means that while the coin is still essentially just “objective information that could be anywhere at once”, in the subjective context of where it is already a coin, there is a limiting factor of time that exists meaning it can't change states at infinite speed and result in a true “everywhere at once” configuration. This shows how the “definitive state” of a coin is a subjective illusion on the part of the observer used to make sense of ever-changing information. Therefore, if the coin is to be flipped within a subjective context it has a 50% chance of NOT being flipped as heads or tails but rather of being MEASURED as heads or tails. In reality it would simply be in a state of “constant change” that is “limited” by the limiter of time.

In this way, the coin can still possess “indeterminate” definitive properties but still be “measured” as being in definitive states at “different times”. This is essentially what time is. Time is the thing that separates an objective entity's infinite number of constantly evolving states into only a finite number of states. In the case of measurement, time is exerted to the extreme where only a “single state” is measured. This explains how from the part of an observer, the past present and future could be divided.

An observer defining the coin as having “future” states simply is a way for the observer to conceive of an entity as having indeterminate states. This occurs when the “information about the state of the coin flip” exists but has not yet been “measured” by the observer. In this way, the “information” that will be used to probabilistically predict the coin's state in the future exists but is constantly changing so can't be measured. However, since the information is already subjectively present there is still an axis of time that exists, albeit one that has less of an effect on the speed of the entity. However, when an entity is “measured”, the entity essentially has infinite time exerted on it and then is viewed as being in only a single state at a time. This is because the delta time T would be infinite in $V = d / t$ which would mean that the velocity V of the entity tends to 0 (because the change in T is infinite since during measurement infinite time is being exerted). This shows how from the perspective of the observer, “the future” is really just information that is already in the observer's subjective context but not yet measured. The “past” similarly would be information that has already been “measured” by the observer and therefore has an 100% certain state. This is why from the perspective of the observer, the past

seems “definite” because it consists of only measured information which was viewed by the observer as having an 100% certain state. The reason the past “feels like the present” to an observer is because the observers brain conceives of information always in the present but then “processes and filters it” in a manner that makes the observer cognitively aware of it “after” the information was already processed.

The observer essentially “subdivides” the coins state in this example into different subjective time periods in order to measure the coin as being definitively in only one state at every point in time. Since the brain can only process “measured information” it needs to conceive of all the changing information in only one single state which means it continuously needs to process information and take time to filter it and make the observer aware of it. In this way, the observer experiences different moments of time based on how this information’s changing states are subdivided into measured definitive ones. How does it know which information to measure? Measured information is simply information that is “infinitely subjective” meaning it is only in one state with an 100% probability of being in that state. This means that the observer doesn’t choose what to measure but merely interprets information that is 100% certain inside of the observers subjective context as “measured”. This measured information is processed by the observers brain and translated by the observer as being in the past simply because its outcome is 100% defined which defines “past entities”.

It would meanwhile be useless for the observer to ask “what side did the coin land on before in the past” since from the observers perspective that state already happened and is 100% decided. This essentially demonstrates how “time” is built up from the subjective contexts of observers in order to “make sense” of fundamentally objectively changing phenomena.

Now what happens if the observer doesn’t know what side the coin landed on in the past? Then wouldn’t from the observers perspective the coin not have an 100% chance of having landed on a specific side and still have a probability associated with its state? Why wouldn’t that be associated by the observer as “happening in the future” then? The answer is, is that to the observer the “past state” of the coin and “future state” of the coin are inherently interchangeable in that they both require “dependent variables” to be examined in order to be ultimately “figured out”. An observers past however is not defined by “what happened to other things” in the past such as a coin, but rather what the observer “experienced in the past”. After all, if the observer does not know the past state of the coin and then “figures it out”, its not like the observer will be going back in time and learning the true state of the coin. Rather the observer is simply defining the future state of the coin that he will observe as “having happened in the past” even though the observer is STILL trying to learn that information in the future. For this reason, the observer associates the coin as having had a certain state in the past simply because the observer correlates the state of the coin with past experience that the observer had that from the context of the observer 100% happened (since they are perceived as in the past). However, in reality from the point of view of the observer, if the observer does not know what happened to the coin in the past, then the observer must always “figure out” that information in the future and not the past. Therefore since the observer is not directly “experiencing” the coin as having flipped in the past but rather only figuring out “which state it did flip” in the future, it is as if from the observers point of view that that past coin flip is something that will occur in the future and not in the past.

This can be likened to velocity. Something still has a definitive position simply because it can be measured without any change in its position. Something moving at a finite speed however would have some certainty to its movement but still can't essentially have its position objectively measured as being in only one state. Finally, something moving at an infinite speed would essentially be "everywhere at once" and therefore have properties that could be "infinitely anything". The past is defined as objective information that inside a subjective configuration is "still" and therefore 100% decided. The future is finitely moving information that is limited by existing within a subjective context yet still can have probabilities associated to its properties and position since the states of its information are "limited" based on the subjective context or "box" it exists within. The "present" would be what is always objectively happening which is simply "infinitely everything at once".

How Information is Dependent on Other Information

Now in the case of a coin, it is fair to ask how it is determined in the first place whether a "coin" will flip as heads or tails. After all what exactly is it that decides the coin's subjective state? Perhaps there can be multiple factors to take into account including what side the coin was grasped from, how heavy the coin is, how thick the coin is, which direction it is flipped, how hard it is flipped, which fingers are being used etc. What this all means is that the "future" state of the coin from the perspective of an observer are decided based on "other informational properties" that interact with the coin. However why is this so? Why does information that interacts with other information become dependent on it in the first place?

In order to make sense of how information is dependent on other information, we must first return to the story of how "objective information" becomes subjective. When an observer "seems" to interact with objective information, what is really happening is that the objective information is infinitely expanding from the point of view of the observer in a way that "allows" for a new "context" to be made sense of where informational entities within that context could take on "real states" and properties. Therefore, from the point of view of the observer, the objective information becomes subjective by entering what is called the observer's "informational world".

Informational Worlds

Informational worlds can be likened to boxes that "limit" objectively infinitely changing information. For example, when a super ball bounces in a borderless space, it is not bouncing but merely "falling" (since there are no walls for it to bounce upon). However, even this notion of entities "falling" or only changing in a single direction is dependent on gravity. Perhaps, in the absence of gravity, the ball simply travels infinitely fast in indeterminate direction (in a borderless space where it exists objectively traveling infinite speed and therefore can be described as everywhere at once). Remember, since indeterminacy been defined previously as simply "an entity existing in multiple states at the same time", this would mean that if the ball is traveling at infinite speed, then the ball must be in "all states" at the same time. Furthermore, if the ball exists in an "objective space" that is infinitely expanding this would mean that the ball does not even need to be "only everywhere at once" but also "everywhere and expanding

infinitely at once". This means that the ball not only doesn't need to have its position definitely defined but also that its position does not even need to be within the defined space in which it is being measured. In fact, the ball could be at places that don't yet exist at the time of measurement because it is in an infinitely expanding space. This would mean that objectively this ball would not need to possess "unitarity" since all of its potential states would not need to equal to 1 because they do not "need" to be in the defined range of space being measured.

Unitarity

Note that generally the probability of an entity's outcome needs to be defined as all of the probabilities associated with all of its possible states added up to equal 1. For example, if a traffic light has a 45 % chance of being green, 45% chance of being red and 10 % chance of being yellow, that would mean that its probabilities (.45+.45+.05) add up to one. This is generally how uncertain outcomes are predicted and defined - as having a probability of possible states that always adds up to 1. This notion of all probability states of an entity adding up to 1 is generally known as "unitarity". What I'm suggesting is that unitarity is a property of subjective informational entities and not objective informational entities. The reason for this being simple - within a subjective context, the possibilities for the states of an objective informational entity are limited and finite. The informational entity cannot simply be "anything at all infinitely expanding" but now has to actually have an outcome state that is "limited" based on the other information that is defined within the subjective context. Furthermore, since subjective contexts are not "infinitely expanding" because they are limited, any informational entity within them must have its outcome states add up to 1 since all of its outcome states need to be inside the "finite" subjective box of information or "subjective informational world". For example, if entities with multiple outcome states are essentially "in both states at once", that would mean that they exist at multiple states at once right? Well, objectively this would be true. However, subjectively because they are "limited" they cannot travel at infinite speed and therefore could not be at "2 places at once" in the same moment of time. Therefore they can still be in 2 places at once but those moments would need to exist at different "subjective times". From here it can be seen how unitarity exists within a subjective context. Even though the information within the context is "objectively infinitely expanding and non-unitary", since the subjective context "limits" the information to only being at one state at one time from the perspective of the observer, then in order to predict the state of an entity subjectively at any one point in time, then its probabilities must add up to 1. This concept of unitarity therefore does not actually mean that the states of entities need to have probabilities that add up to one overall but rather only at separate points in a subjectively defined dimension of "time".

The way that observers "view" information is with their brains which essentially "process" information within their informational worlds and then "realize" it as existing as in the present when in fact they really observed that information in the past. However, since their brains cannot conceive of information in the "present", it processes it and then "shows" it to the observer as definitive since it has actually taken place in the past and not the present. This is why information to an observer is always in a definitive state - because their brains shows them the past information which is always 100% decided.

Informational Worlds and Information Interactions

Observers each exist within their own subjective “informational worlds” which are connected to the “informational worlds” of the other entities they interact with. Inside of these informational worlds consist of “information” that is limited because it is subjectified. It is therefore inside of a limited “boxed” space instead of a space that is “unboxed” or limitless. This means that the information can’t be in “any possible state at once”, but rather is “confined” to only be in states that align with the existing information in its “informational world”. All of the information inside of an informational must be “consistent” in this way just as puzzle pieces must be consistent with one another to combine into an entire whole puzzle. In this way, the informational “pieces” must have “shapes” or in this case properties that are consistent one another in order to exist within the same informational world.

This also explains how time comes to be. Inside of these informational worlds time exists simply because the information inside of the informational world is not changing states at “infinite speed” but is now “limited” by the limits of the informational world it is in. Time IS that measure of limited-ness. It is described by how “limited” an entities state is. If the entities state is definitive then time exists infinitely for that entity since it is “infinitely limited” and can never change (in $V = d/t$, if an entity is unchangeable its velocity would equal 0 which means t would tend to infinity). If however, the information In the informational world is still “indeterminate” then it would have a finite velocity and therefore would have a finite time. Inside of informational worlds there is always a “limited amount of information” so information can never change states at a “infinite velocity” since there will be states of the information that simply don’t exist subjectively inside that context or informational world.

Now inside of these informational worlds, there also exist sub-informational worlds which can be used to divide the “worlds” of different subjective observers. These sub-informational worlds have information that is changing “around” and nearer to them in the informational world and therefore interacts with them. For example, if interaction is governed by locality then when information inside a informational world changes at a finite rate it has a certain probability of changing into a position that is near another observers informational world. This essentially is paramount to an interaction between the 2 “informational worlds” which essentially forces the information and the other informational world of the observer to “coalesce” in a deterministic local manner. These two informational worlds then combine into “one larger informational world” with more information. Informational worlds in this sense can simply be defined as “subjective spaces where informational entities are dependent on one another”. This means that in order for 2 informational entities to be in the same informational world they must have properties that are at least somewhat dependent on the properties of the other. In this way their properties are “entangled” and therefore part of the same “informationally dependent context”.

The Geometry of Informational Worlds and Quantum Entanglement

Another question that can be asked is why does locality define how informational entities interact in informational worlds? The reason for this is because informational worlds are perhaps governed by geometry. This means that the information within them are not “individual

particles” but rather geometric entities that are capable of symmetrically fitting into one another. Therefore, when information “fits” symmetrically with other information, the combined information becomes “dependent” one another’s state. The states of the two informational entities become “entangled” in this way which can account for how quantum particles seem to become entangled and have their properties dependent on one another after interacting.

Moreover, how the informational states of these entities are actually determined when measured could be likened to puzzle pieces. If informational worlds themselves are “puzzles” then every bit of information can be considered a “geometric piece” that fits in with other pieces of this puzzle. Therefore when changing information interacts with other information in this puzzle it must do so in a way that “symmetrically fits” into it. This means that the information will take on properties based on how it “fits” in with the existing of information of the sub-informational world it is interacting with. In this way when two informational entities interact, they are “conspiring” their outcome states to fit cohesively in a geometrically consistent manner.

For example, in quantum mechanics when a 0 spin particle is “split” into 2 particles, the 2 particles are entangled in that they have states that together must add up to 0. Therefore if one is measured as -1, the other automatically needs to be measured as +1. Informational worlds explain this phenomenon by likening the 2 particles to geometric puzzle pieces that change state continuously in an informational world. If there is 1 informational particle that is “definitive” in that it is measured as being spin -1, then from the context of the observer who measured it, the other informational entity must “fit” geometrically into the puzzle of the observers sub-informational world. In order to do so it must automatically have a spin of +1 in order to “make sense” in the observers informational world.

This can also be another way to conceive of time. If entities being “definitive” in terms of their informational states result in “measurement” by the observer of the informational world they’re in, then it makes sense from the perspective of that observer why any other information in that informational world must be aligned with that already measured information. Simply because, when the measured information is measured it experiences infinite time and takes up more space in the informational world of the observer. Therefore, the other information must geometrically fall into place soon after just as how when more of a puzzle is complete, pieces could be more easily “added” and fit into the puzzle. It is the “gaps” in the puzzle that define the finite state of information in an informational world.

If an informational entity interacts with another informational entity there is a combination of their two informational worlds. This means that the information from one informational world enters a new informational world and then must take on states that are consistent with that informational world “geometrically”. This means that if the existing sub-informational world is a puzzle with certain sized pieces missing, the new information that enters that context “takes on” the shapes of those pieces in order to fit into the new combined informational world. Therefore inside the informational world of the observer, the observers information interacts with other information (since inside informational worlds there are separate times because the information is limited) and therefore once the information interact with one another, it causes them to “narrow” their potential states. This essentially is how a sequence of time is “noticed” by an observer as the interactions of newer and newer informational worlds combining when

interacting. The information that is geometrically “stuck” in the informational world has no uncertainty associated with its state. “Stuck” in this sense simply means that the information has no uncertainty regarding its states because it is “totally confined” by the geometric shapes of the other information in its informational world and therefore has “no room to move”. Since it has no room to move, it has no room to change and therefore must have a “definite certain” state. Since time is the measure of “limitedness” to movement or “certainty”, infinite time can be said to be exerted on it. It can then be measured by the brain because it is completely certain in its properties.

This explains how a sequence of moments on the part of the observer are observed. Remember that objectively this information the observer interacts with is always infinitely changing. However inside the context of the informational world that the observer is in it is finitely changing, and from the perspective of the observer when measured it is “unchanging” or being “infinitely limited” by the limiting factor of change also known as time. This is because it is infinitely “limited” and confined by the geometry of its informational world. See the following schematic for further explanation:

The states and properties of information inside an informational world can be compared to shapes and are entirely dependent on the shapes of the other information within that informational world that they are in. Therefore, in the image on the left, the puzzle piece that is missing is not yet “inside of the informational world” but when it enters it its “shape” will already be determined based on the “shapes” of the other informational entities in its informational world (or the puzzle).

Causality and the Constant Speed C (of Light)

Now that it is explained why information is “dependent” on other information and why they take on finite properties within informational worlds, it is fair to ask why information is perceived as “sequentially at all”. After all, if moments consist of “stuck” informational worlds that are certain, then why do different “informational worlds” need to exist sequentially at all? Why does it seem like “information” in a single moment causes another moment when in fact the two are simply informational geometric entities?

The reason that there is “causality” in this way is because “2 things cant happen at once” in a subjective world. The reason for this is simply because “time” is present to make the states of entities limited and only finitely changing. Because finitely changing entities can’t be in 2 places at once (since that would require them to be infinitely changing or have an infinite velocity), this would mean that in the “subjective” worlds of observers entities cannot be in 2 states at the same time. This ultimately governs the concept of “causality” in the classical world. If 2 things cant happen at the same time instance, then they must be separated into different moments. It is

then perceived as if the information states of entities in past moments (which are 100% decided) precede future moments (which are decided only per probability) and therefore “cause” them.

Additionally, this can explain the phenomenon of why no information in the universe travels faster than “light speed”. Perhaps, the universe is itself is one giant “subjective informational world” that itself has defined borders. Therefore, the reason the speed of light is what it is because that simply defines the speed at which information propagates throughout the “limitation” of the specific subject context that this universe is in. This can be conceived of by imagining the classical behavior of a continuously bouncing super-balls confined to a box. If a super-ball is in a larger box then it has the potential to “bounce” faster than if it is in a small box. This is because there is a lesser likelihood it will “hit a wall” and have its speed stopped. The same concept can be applied to universes. Universes are essentially “informational worlds” themselves and each subjective instances of the objective everything that exists. Since they are subjective instances they are essentially “limited” in terms of the information they possess and are “boxed” in this way. Now if one universe has the potential to contain more information than a smaller universe then perhaps it will have a larger box which means the super-ball could bounce faster. It seems that in this universe, the limit of the bouncing of the metaphorical super-ball is what is defined as the “speed of light”.

It should be noted though that since each observer has a “sub-informational world” that their information is associated with inside of the larger informational world of the universe they will have “different information” within their worlds than other observers in the universe. However they will still both be part of the “larger informational world” of the universe which means that their measured information must always be consistent one another. This is why one observer cant measure the speed of light as different than other, it is the same for both of them because the information associated with it needs to be consistent in the larger informational world of the universe they both exist in. For this reason, they “measure” it in the same manner.

Why Does Entropy Increase With Time?

This can also explain why from the perspective of observers, the amount of uncertainty in their universe always increases with their perception of time moving. If time moves from the perspective of the observer because their informational worlds are “seemingly interacting” with more and more information that means that the properties of the informational entities within their informational worlds are constantly becoming more and more complex. For example, if there was only 3 informational entities in the informational world of an observer it would be easy for the observer to eventually “measure” all 3 of their properties since it would be easy for them to “get stuck” and have the configurations of their possible properties definitively measured. However when more interactions happen, the properties of informational entities are dependent on more and more informational entities thus making the state of information overall more complex and therefore from the point of view of the observer “increasing in entropy”.

It should be noted that objectively the information is finitely changing within an infinite world, but since observers cant “measure” changing information they only “know the states” of the information they “experience” definitively which is the information that has an 100% defined property. This is the information that they “measure” and therefore the information they

experience. When it is said that “informational worlds” interact and therefore result in more measurements by the observer, what it really means is that more informational worlds are fitting in with one another essentially creating more informational entities to take on decided states and therefore more informational entities to experience increased “time”. However, entropy increases because even though the states of these entities become “more certain objectively” from the perspective of observers, since observers only can “view” measured certain information, this information that they measure becomes dependent on more and more informational entities within other sub-informational worlds which means that them “trying to determine the nature of the states of entities that they HAVEN’T YET MEASURED (or future information from their point of view because it hasn’t yet been measured) becomes more difficult for them. This is why from their perspective entropy and uncertainty always increases.

Summary - How Observers Conceive of Information

To summarize, the way that observers are able to “cognitive conceive” of information is by their brains processing that information within their subjective context or “informational world” that is 100% decided and “measuring” it. This measurement of information means that the information being measured is subject to infinite time which means it can only exist in one state. Therefore, in the sub-informational world of that observer, the information is “neatly packed” and cannot change states at all since it is infinitely confined. This can be likened to how anything inside of a box that is a small enough size (or tight enough) essentially won't have any room to move and therefore would be still. Information with an 100% defined state is essentially “confined” to sub-informational worlds that are small enough to only fit the geometrically static information alone. This means that all of the information in such a “confined sub-informational world” must be in one static state because it is “infinitely limited” and has no room to change. In this way it is bound to infinite time since time itself is just a measure of limitedness on an entity’s ability to change states. This state of “infinite limitedness” where the information is in an 100% certain state of itself “can” actually be processed by the brain since it is measured. This neatly packed information then is translated by the brain as a “moment”.

This is essentially why moments are perceived by observers as being “definitive”. Since the brain can only process measured information, the information cannot “change” within that moment in which it is processed. The information is essentially a still “snapshot” in the context of the brain which means that it can never “change” no matter how much time passes (in this way it is subject to infinite time). From these “still snapshots” observers fashion a consistent stream of experience which explains how they “exist” inside their observational worlds.

Moreover, the reason that observers “cognitively realize” only definitive information is because that is the measured information that the brain could process. Since any information with a totally certain state needs to be equated with the “past” by an observer, the observer actually classically interacts with a “past” that has information already processed by the brain and not the present. The true present would be an objective state where everything is in all possible states at once and always happening. From the perspective of an observer, even though this “present” is the only thing that exists, they cannot interact with all its objective information at once and

therefore need to subjectify and categorize it as having occurred in the past in order to interact with it.

Conclusion

In this paper I discussed how different levels of subjectivity (from objective to infinitely subjective) define the experience of time and the configurations of information.

The below schematic can demonstrate how these different levels of subjectivity results in different perceptions of time, informational probability and velocity.

Tiers of Subjectivity

- Objective (infinite time)
- Informational World (finite time)
- Measured (infinite time)

No Borders;
limitations, No Time;
Entity Changes
Infinitely Fast -
Objective state of
information; Defines
the true present

Finite Borders; Finite
limitations, Finite
Time; Entity Changes
at Finite Speeds;
information inside
informational world
not yet measured;
Defines Future

Infinite Borders; Infinite
limitations, Infinite Time;
Entity Changes at 0 Speed;
Still; measured; Defines Past
which from the perspective of
observers also defines the
“cognitively defined present”